

STUDIES IN MONOCYCLIC SESQUITERPENES. AN UNAMBIGUOUS SYNTHESIS OF *ar*-TURMERONE

By SAILENDRA MOHAN MUKHERJEE

ar-Turmerone, the aromatic ketone obtained from *Curcuma longa*, has been synthesised by an unambiguous method.

The occurrence in natural oils of sesquiterpenes and their derivatives accompanied by related aromatic derivatives is rather uncommon. It is therefore of particular interest that the elegant investigations of Rupe (Rupe, Clar, Pfan and Plattner, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1934, 17, 372) have shown that the oil from the tubers of *Curcuma longa* contains a ketone having aromatic characteristics. The ketone has been named *ar*-Turmerone (I). A sesquiterpene ketone, turmerone, has also been shown to be present in the curcuma oil. It is represented by (II)

The most important experiment in the elucidation of the constitution of *ar*-turmerone (I) is its treatment with methanolic caustic potash, when acetone and curcumone (III) are obtained. This fission at the double bond on treatment with alkali is characteristic of the $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated ketones. Curcumone has been synthesised by Rupe and Wieder-Kehr (*ibid.*, 1924, 7, 654) by treatment of the acid chloride of β -(*p*-tolyl)-butyric acid with zinc methyl.

On catalytic hydrogenation in presence of nickel catalyst *ar*-turmerone affords a dihydro derivative, also synthesised by Rupe and Gassmann (*ibid.*, 1936, 19, 569) by three different methods. From the synthetical point of view these syntheses establish the constitution of *ar*-turmerone except the position of the double bond in the side-chain.

Rupe and Gassmann (*loc. cit.*) have also synthesised *ar*-turmerone bycondensing curcumone (III) with acetone in presence of dry sodium

ethoxide. But it will be observed on scrutiny that the above method of synthesis of *ar*-turmerone is capable of giving rise to other compounds having the structures (IV) and (V), so that it is not free from ambiguity.

(IV)

(V)

So it was thought desirable to synthesise *ar*-turmerone by a method which might leave no doubt about its constitution.

The present method, described in the following lines, starts from α -(*p*-tolyl)-propionaldehyde (VI) which, in its turn, is prepared from *p*-tolylmethyl ketone following the procedure of Dutta (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 18, 233). Reduction of the above aldehyde (VI) was first attempted with sodium and moist ether, but the yield was not satisfactory owing to the appreciable formation of the corresponding pinacol. The alcohol (VII) is then obtained in good yield by reducing the aldehyde (VI) with zinc dust and acetic acid. Conversion of the alcohol (VII) into the corresponding bromide (VIII) is accomplished in the usual way by means of phosphorus tribromide or 48% hydrobromic acid, the latter reagent giving a better yield. The Grignard complex, prepared from the bromide (VIII), on being allowed to react upon the piperidide of $\beta\beta$ -dimethylacrylic acid according to the condition laid down by Rupe and Gassmann (*loc. cit.*), gives the desired ketone (I).

The above Grignard reagent is allowed to react upon β -methylcrotono-nitrile under the conditions of Butenandt and Schmidt-Thomé (*Ber.*, 1938, 71, 1487) when the ketone (I) is obtained in better yield.

(VI)

(VII)

(VIII)

In this connection, it is rather interesting to note that the semicarbazone or the hydrazone of *ar*-turmerone (I) on reduction according to Wolff-Kishner

method is expected to give α -*curcumene* which has been ascribed the structure (IX) by Simonsen *et al.* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 1504 ; 1940, 451) based on analytical as well as synthetical data. The present work may be schematically represented thus :

E X P E R I M E N T A L

β -(*p*-Tolyl)-propyl Alcohol (VII).—Zinc dust (65 g.) in small portions was added during 2 hours to a solution of α -(*p*-tolyl)-propionaldehyde (VI, 30 g.) in acetic acid (300 c.c.). Then the whole mixture was heated on the sand-bath for 36 hours. After decanting the liquid from the zinc-sludge most of the acetic acid was nearly neutralised with dilute caustic soda solution so that the mixture remained just acidic. The liquid was then extracted with ether, the ether-extract combined with the ether washings of zinc-sludge, washed with water and then dried (Na_2SO_4). The residue left after the removal of ether gave on distillation the desired product (27 g.), free from aldehydic smell, b. p. $102^{\circ}/5$ mm. (Found : C, 79.82 ; H, 9.26. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}$ requires C, 80.0 ; H, 9.33 per cent).

β -(*p*-Tolyl)-propyl Bromide (VIII).—A mixture of the above alcohol (27 g.), hydrobromic acid (48%, 60 c.c.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (10 c.c.) was refluxed for 4 hours. The cooled reaction mixture was diluted and the heavy layer extracted with ether, the ethereal layer washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and water and then dried (CaCl_2). After the solvent was driven off, the residue on distillation gave the bromo derivative (VIII) passing over at $88^{\circ}/6$ mm, yield 32 g. (Found : Br, 37.08. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{13}\text{Br}$ requires Br, 37.5 per cent).

***ar*-Turmerone (I).**—Magnesium (2 g.) was dried in *vacuo* and taken in ether (5 c.c.) and to this was added 0.5 c.c. of methyl iodide to start the reaction. Then the above bromide (VIII, 10 g.) in ether (10 c.c.) was added dropwise during half-an-hour, the flask being heated on the water-bath. After this the mixture was refluxed for further 1 hour to complete the formation of the Grignard complex. To this boiling mixture was then added β -methylcrotono-nitrile (5 g.), the ether driven off and thiophen-free benzene (10 c.c.) introduced. The refluxing was

continued for 4 hours after which the yellowish ketimino compound was decomposed in the cold with acetic acid and the mixture heated for 15 minutes. Water was then added and heated for further 15 minutes. The cooled mixture was then extracted with ether, the ether-benzene layer washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and water and then dried. After the evaporation of the solvent, the residue was fractionated in vacuum when the desired ketone (I) passed over at $158^{\circ}/8$ mm. (lit. b. p. $159-60^{\circ}/10$ mm.). (Found: C, 82.96; H, 9.1. $C_{15}H_{20}O$ requires C, 83.33; H, 9.26 per cent).

The *semicarbazone*, prepared in the usual way, first separated as a thick heavy oil and then solidified after a very long time (2 months). After crystallisation from dilute alcohol it melts at 106° (lit. m. p. $108-109^{\circ}$). (Found: N, 15.26. $C_{16}H_{23}ON_3$ requires N, 15.38 per cent).

Piperidide of $\beta\beta$ -Dimethylacrylic Acid.— $\beta\beta$ -Dimethylacrylic acid (20 g.) was treated with thionyl chloride (16 c.c.) and the solution kept overnight after which the excess thionyl chloride was driven off by the water pump. The residue was then distilled when the acid chloride of $\beta\beta$ -dimethylacrylic acid came over at 118° , yield 19 g.

The above acid chloride (19 g.) was added with shaking to piperidine (40 g.), well cooled in ice, when vigorous reaction took place. After standing for half an hour the mixture was diluted with water, extracted with ether, the ethereal extract washed with dilute sulphuric acid, water and then dried. The solvent being removed, the residue was distilled in vacuum when 28 g. of the piperidide, b.p. $92^{\circ}/10$ mm., were obtained. (Found: N, 8.24. $C_{10}H_{17}ON$ requires N, 8.38 per cent).

Grignard Reaction with the Piperidide of $\beta\beta$ -Dimethylacrylic Acid.—To the Grignard complex, prepared from 10 g. of the bromide (VIII), 2 g. of Mg and 10 c.c. ether, were added in the cold with shaking 9 g. of the piperidide of $\beta\beta$ -dimethylacrylic acid. After driving off the ether 10 c.c. of thiophen-free benzene were added and the mixture refluxed for 4 hours. The cold reaction mixture was then decomposed with dilute acetic acid, heated for 15 minutes on the water-bath, then diluted with water and extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed with cold dilute hydrochloric acid, sodium bicarbonate solution, water and then dried. The residue left after the evaporation of the solvent was fractionated in vacuum when the desired ketone (I) was obtained in poor yield and came over at $156^{\circ}/7$ mm. (Found: C, 82.86; H, 9.21. $C_{15}H_{20}O$ requires C, 83.33; H, 9.26 per cent).

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